

Hybrid Ceramic Polymer Electrolytes Enabling Long Cycling in Practical 1 Ah-Class High-Voltage Solid-State Batteries with Li Metal Anode

Nicola Boaretto,^{1,*} Leire Meabe,¹ Simon Lindberg,¹ Haritz Perez-Furundarena,¹ Itziar Aldalur,¹ Elias Lobato,¹ Francisco Bonilla,¹ Izaskun Combarro,² Antonio Gutiérrez-Pardo,² Andriy Kvasha,² Marine Lechartier,³ Rémi Vincent,³ Jérôme Cognard,³ Sylvie Genies,³ Lise Daniel,³ María Martínez-Ibañez^{1,*}

¹ Centre for Cooperative Research on Alternative Energies, CIC energiGUNE, Basque Research and Technology Alliance (BRTA), Alava Technology Park, Albert Einstein 48, Vitoria-Gasteiz 01510, Spain

² CIDETEC, Basque Research and Technology Alliance (BRTA), Paseo de Miramon 196, Donostia-San Sebastian 20014, Spain

³ Univ. Grenoble Alpes, CEA, Liten, DEHT, 38000 Grenoble, France

Figure S1. a) Scheme of 1 Ah pouch cell assembling process. b – d) Assembly of the safety test device: b) Cu plate, thermal insulation layer, and heating pad; c) the 1 Ah cell sandwiched between Cu plates with a thermocouple on the top; d) final stack wrapped in fiberglass cloth.

Figure S2. Cross-section SEM images of the HCPE between two Li electrodes, collected with the backscattered electron detector at an acceleration of 2 keV: a) whole stack at a magnification of 600 \times ; b) the two layers of the HCPE, at a magnification of 1200 \times ; c) interface between the polyolefin separator and the Li electrode, at 2400 \times ; d) interface between the LATP-rich layer and the Li electrode, at 5000 \times ; e) interface between the two layers of the HCPE, at magnification of 5000 \times ; f) LATP-rich layer of the HCPE, at 10000 \times .

Figure S3. Mechanical properties of Celgard 2500 separator in a) longitudinal, and b) transversal direction, respect to the stretching direction; c) summary of the mechanical properties.

Figure S4. Selected voltage relaxation profiles after the potentiostatic polarization experiment at 60 °C. The slope is used to determine the salt restricted diffusion coefficient (shown in the figure) with equation 4).

Figure S5. Galvanostatic cycling of HCPE in Li||Li cells, at 60 °C, with plated/stripped capacity of 1 mAh cm⁻², and current density of 0.1 mA cm⁻² (C/10).

Figure S6. Galvanostatic cycling of unsupported HCPE in Li||Li cells, at 60 °C and 1 mAh cm⁻². C-rates are referred to a plated capacity of 1 mAh cm⁻². The red asterisks indicate the first voltage instabilities in each experiment. a) Critical current density test (one cycle at C/10, C/5, C/3, C/2, C/1, and long cycling at C/10; b) long cycling at 0.1 mA cm⁻² (C/10), with a 50 μm-thick HCPE membrane; c) long cycling at 0.1 mA cm⁻² (C/10), with a 100 μm-thick HCPE membrane.

Figure S7. EDS spectra of the different phases in the EDS phase mapping of an uncycled Li|HCPE|Li cell (Figure 5a). a) "PE" phase; b) "LATP" phase; c) "PE/LATP" phase; d) "Li-metal"; and e) "Celgard" phase.

Figure S8. EDS spectra of the different phases in the EDS phase mapping of a Li|HCPE|Li cell cycled at a capacity of 1 mAh cm^{-2} (**Figure 5b**). a) "Celgard" phase; b) "PE" phase; c) "Li-metal" phase; d) "LATP"; e) "Li-O rich" phase; and f) "PE/LATP" phase.

Figure S9. EDS spectra of the different phases in the EDS phase mapping of a Li|HCPE|Li cell cycled at a capacity of 3 mAh cm⁻² (**Figure 5c**). a) "SEI 2" phase; b) "PE" phase; c) "Li-metal" phase; d) "Celgard"; e) "LATP" phase; and f) "SEI 1" phase.

Figure S10. Compositional mapping of Li (red), O (blue) and P (purple and green) in cross-sections of Li||Li cells with HCPE as electrolyte: pristine cell (left); after ten cycles at 0.1 mA cm^{-2} and with cycled capacity of 1 mAh cm^{-2} (center); after ten cycles at a fixed capacity of 3 mAh cm^{-2} (right).

Figure S11. Cyclability of NMC-811|HCPE|Li cells with unsupported HCPE, cycled at 60 °C, between 4.3 V and 3.0 V: a) specific discharge capacity (left axis) and coulombic efficiency (right axis); b) voltage profiles at different C-rates; c) differential capacity profiles at different C-rates; d) voltage curves vs. capacity during cycling at C/10; e) differential capacity profiles during cycling at C/10.

Figure S12. Specific discharge capacity (left axis) and coulombic efficiency (right axis) of two NMC8-11|HCPE|Li coin cells with unsupported HCPE, cycled at a) 40 °C; b) 25 °C.

Figure S13. Voltage vs. capacity profiles and differential capacity profiles of a NMC-811||Li cell, cycled at 60 °C (Figure 7a,b): a) differential capacity profiles at different C-rates; c) voltage curves vs. capacity during cycling at C/10; d) differential capacity profiles during cycling at C/10.

Figure S14. Specific discharge capacity (left axis) and coulombic efficiency (right axis) of a NMC-811|HCPE|Li monolayer pouch cell cycled at 60 °C, C/10, in the voltage range between 3.0 and 4.2 V, and with applied initial torque of 0.3 N m; b) selected charge/discharge voltage curves.

Figure S15. Comparison between the EIS spectra of a three-electrode pouch cell instrumented with LFP reference electrode and of a cell without reference electrode, at 4.1 V (89% SoC) (60 °C, 3 kg cm⁻², 0.28 mA cm⁻², frequency (x) = 10^x Hz).

Figure S16. Comparison between the EIS spectra of 60 mAh and 11 mAh single layer cells, in two electrode configuration, at a) 3.0 V (0% SoC), b) 3.9 V (75% SoC), c) 4.1 V (89% SoC), and d) 4.2 V (100% SoC); e) EIS spectrum of a 1 Ah cell at 30% SoC.

Table S1. Cycling performance (cyclability) of HV-LPBs with solid polymer electrolytes (SPEs) and gel-polymer electrolytes (GPEs, greyed entries), and with cathode loadings higher than 10 mg cm⁻². CAM: cathode active material. The cycle life was calculated as the number of cycles corresponding to a capacity retention of 80%. In the cases in which the cycling was interrupted before reaching 80% capacity retention, the total number of cycles performed was indicated.

CAM type	CAM loading / mg cm⁻²	Cycle life	Initial sp. Cap. / mAh g⁻¹	C-rate (charge)	Cycling temp. / °C	Type	Ref.
NMC-811	21	100	177	C/10	50	SPE	[30]
NMC-622	23	100	163	C/10	50	SPE	[30]
NMC-532	10.5	150	150	C/10	25	SPE	[31]
NMC-811	10.5	100	205	C/10	30	GPE	[32]
NMC-811	13.5	100	NA	C/4	25	GPE	[33]
NMC-811	12.5	80	200	C/5	30	GPE	[34]
NMC-811	14	40	150	C/5	25	SPE	[35]
NMC-811	12	8	200	C/20	40	SPE	[36]
LCO	14	200	174	C/2	25	GPE	[37]
NMC-622	10.3	50	152	C/20	30	SPE	[38]
NMC-622	10	300	150	C/5	25	GPE	[39]
NMC-811	17.7	236	210	C/5	25	GPE	[40]
NMC-811	20	200	240	C/2	25	GPE	[41]
LCO	17.4	700	170	C/2	25	GPE	[42]
NMC-811	15	25	175	C/10	25	SPE	[43]
NMC-811	10.6	100	161	C/5	40	GPE	[44]
NMC-811	14.7	110	150	C/10	60	SPE	This work